

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DEBESAI****FIRST NAME: ISAYAS****PROGRAM CODE: LLM****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2013 on Windows 7

THE WORLD OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Reading the coursepack for the first period, which is a compilation of three to four sources; reminds me of my Bachelor of Laws (LLB) final thesis paper. One of the difficult tasks in writing my thesis paper was to achieve conformity to the Bluebook style of citation. I remember having to deal with lots of sources on different mediums and getting to know on how to cite them. I was not really acquainted with citation things until I enter for my LLB. However, upon its completion and having to write a paper, I could say I have gained fair amount of knowledge of the citation world.

By the time I continued my education into law school and having to write multiple papers in a semester, I was really into it. However, all this was based on a piece of reference paper, which was not more than three pages given to us by one instructor. Due to the pace of the courses given to us, it can be said we have not invested in this subject as it should be, which now I can see that it can take a whole course in itself. Now, having to continue my Master of Laws (LLM), it seems I have to deep my feet if I am going to join the world of written academia.

2) SUMMARY OF COURSEPACK ONE

This first coursepack given in the first period of the ACA-401 course relates to an 83-paged general introduction with regard to: essay writing, citations, plagiarism, crucial rules of thumb to remember when writing, common English errors, style guides, comparison between US and UK English, the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) and

Turabian style guide to follow, some practical examples using the Turabian referencing, as well as some Latin abbreviations together with its expressions. Finally, a video lecture on the topics of Zotero, templates and styling are included (EUCLID 2015).

3) MAIN POINTS OF DISCUSSION

The coursepack starts with the general form of essay writing. According to the coursepack, when preparing to write an essay, identifying the question, conduct researching, organizing ideas, writing the essay, referencing, final editing and handing over of the essay are some of the steps that should be followed (EUCLID 2015, 2-6). These topics are given with brief summary in their own to let us know what each of these sub-topics hold on. On the issue of procrastination, I cannot over emphasize that it worries me much whenever I try to write for the best of me.

The next topic talks about plagiarism and citations. These topics discuss on the issue of plagiarism and how it can be avoided with the proper citation of a source. However, the frequency of citation itself, the types of citations, how, why, and when to quote or paraphrase a source, even using a signal phrase, as well as the style of citations is to be taken carefully. I now know when to use between the two citation methods: the in-text citation and list of works cited, but also when not to cite (EUCLID 2015, 15). I find it important that when a certain knowledge is commonly found in many sources or articles, it is better not to cite which would make the writing process somehow easier.

Having discussed ten rules of thumb to consider when writing an essay (EUCLID 2015, 43-45), the coursepack introduces another importance of much wider issue. This relates to an English grammar revision (EUCLID 2015, 46-51). It talks about the most common English errors such as placement of the comma, use of adjectives, difference between “that” and “which,” how to avoid mixing between alpha-numerals in a text, and many others. This topic which can be said touched on the surface is really one of the most intriguing and exhausting one. I have to say when the topic of English and grammar are raised, it would drag me to its own world of planetary. Most of the time, things get clumsy when I am faced with those grammar things that for a while follow a certain rule and later on tend to be irregular in following that same rule. What I find perplexing is that, when I try to comprehend with similar grammar formalities in different contexts, such as the case of prepositions in itself, most of the time I cannot differentiate on some issues. What I usually try to do is having to maintain the tonality of the sentence to hear it internally to establish for its readability. However, for a more hair-splitting assurance, I usually prefer to google for the Internet.

The topic that discusses on the issue of style guideline is another most important one. Among the many issues raised, it discusses that style addresses more than grammar and punctuation, by differentiating it to include all the citation method, sentence length, indentation, use of US or UK based English, institution tailored guideline and so on. On the usefulness of having a style guideline, the coursepack asserts on the establishment of common understanding in consistency, impersonality as well as establishing a common ground in the case of texts having to involve many contributors. The issue of having to

follow many different style guides to address different audiences or preferences can bring its own complexities. Although the coursepack limits itself mentioning such as The Economist style guide, The Chicago Manual of Style, the BBC News style, among others (EUCLID 2015, 53), it seems to me that although following a style guide is crucial, having to learn as a subject with the vastness of the reference guide for three to four style guidelines can bring its own complications.

The topic on the comparison of American vs. British English, lists some of the common variations that a writer should be aware of (EUCLID 2015, 54). To mention some, the difference, issues of pronunciation, spelling, grammar, etc. are mentioned. Without knowing of such differences and especially with some of the geographical or colloquial words, one can say the message is delivered with its quirks. The issue of having to address multiple audiences with different background and of a magnitude cultural and sociological aspects cannot be more than easy even for an experienced writer. May be targeting your audience and thereby minimizing any misunderstanding using such institutionalized guideline could be one of the cures though with some tradeoffs.

On the case of CMS and Turabian discussion, both the usage formality together with some of the common examples is presented (EUCLID 2015, 66). The Crib Sheet mentions on the common writing style we should follow. Such can be mentioned like abbreviations, capitalization, compound words, italics and quotation marks, quotations, using the Turabian footnoting, indenting, line-spacing, etc. It can be said that my understanding with these different types of style following to be incomplete and not coherent. However, with the use of the Turabian guide, which essentially is the Chicago style, would benefit me for most of my papers in order to communicate with the world of academia in a coherent style.

The coursepack has delivered to us some common practical examples of thesis style referencing (EUCLID 2015, 71-77). It brings some guidance on the use of margins, fonts, indents, paper size, line spacing, headings, endnote and footnotes, bibliography, and son that are based on the Turabian style. Towards the end of the coursepack, it highlights on the common Latin abbreviations and their meanings (EUCLID 2015, 78-83). Although I came to know some of the terms due to the nature of my law background, I can say, I have learned more than few new abbreviation meanings such as “e.g.,” “et al.,” “et. Seq.,” “i.e.,” “sic,” “v.v.,” among others.

There is a EUCLID video on the use of templates and usage of style based on Microsoft Office Word. Although the video is brief and presented in a single product preference, it gives an idea from the perspective of a style guideline to work with. (EUCLID), There is also a video which shows on practical use of a Zotero software which is something brought by the technology of our times as a rescue in the task of referencing (EUCLID 2017). In my previous workings, I used to save my references using a software called scrapbook. However, Zotero seems to be much tailored and specialized mainly for referencing. I hope to have a good working time with this new software soon.

4) CHALLENGING TOPICS

The challenging issues I found include, the subject with returning back to English grammar writing. Such can be mentioned in the area of placement of the comma, use of adjectives, and the difference between that and which among the few. The most striking one was with having to adhere to one form of English, either US or UK based which I am not accustomed of. This reminds me of my time with English 101, which I had great pleasures and its many displeasures in mastering the English grammar with all its irregular rules to follow.

Needless to say, the issue of “that,” “which,” and the proper use of the “,” are as always taking their levels of challenges. It brings the attention of having to deal with these issues, especially when coming from different background of study than the standard way of English writing. Having acquainted with certain writing style of my legal background, which in certain way deflect from the normal writing is a challenge for me to make my writing comprehensible to a non-legal person in an easily digestible form.

5) NEW THINGS LEARNED

Although this 83-paged coursepack seems to present few pages, it has raised a condensed and briefly discussed topics which in itself needs time to get into its details. The new things that I have learned from this first period coursepack is that, I used not to differentiate and even not to give credit to such formality to the differences between the American and British way of academic writing. I can see now that there is a sizable difference in their writings and the many other variances I should put into consideration. Such can be mentioned on the difference between fast sailing and fast sailing (EUCLID 2015, 68). The difference seems almost negligible, however according to my new understanding, I came to know that there is a real difference in their meaning. I understood that one has to be very careful in his/her academic writings so as not to be misunderstood by a familiarized audience accustomed to a style such as the CMS or the Turabian way of styling.

Another issue that I thought I knew but not in another form is the use of “,” before “and” such as when listing items (EUCLID 2015, 48-45). To this day, I was not aware of such use. However, now I can write comfortably although without perfection using “,” and” format, which is promoted with the writer of the coursepack (EUCLID 2015, 48).

6) CONCLUSION

The lesson I have learned from this coursepack is that, on the issue of academic writing, I am expected to be proficient enough at conveying my message. Having fulfilled all the requirements in adopting a style guide, I have learned quite a lot starting from writing my essay, enriching it with citations, and presenting it in a well-structured grammar form. From now onwards, having to base on a standardized styling guideline, I am planning

on developing my skills in order to produce a smooth, coherent, and engaging paper with my subsequent academic writings. If I am to be considered an academician and my voice to be heard in the academic arena, then I am bound to master what is offered in this coursepack and the periods that will follow in this course.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Retrieved from: <http://www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>, (October 21, 2019).

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